

Innovative approach to lithium extraction: Integrating COOL+ process with sustainable solid waste management

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Lithium is a strategic and indispensable material for future technologies where the demand for Li-ion batteries is constantly increasing (Martin et al. 2017), (Pavón et al. 2021b). Extracting Li from primary sources is challenging since it does not occur in an elementary state but either as a trace element in a firmly bound structure in the form of α -spodumene, $\text{LiAlSi}_2\text{O}_6$, which is the most economically exploitable lithium-bearing mineral and is widely used for the extraction of such key metal (Abdullah et al. 2019), (Nazir et al. 2022). While most processes deal with lithium extraction from primary sources using environmentally inconceivable chemicals, such as H_2SO_4 , HF, HCl, and NaOH (Dessemond et al. 2020), (Gao et al. 2022), the COOL+ process (CO₂ leaching process) uses water and CO₂ to selectively leach Li from any silicate mineral. This approach is an environmentally friendly route to battery-grade Li_2CO_3 with a zero-waste principle because the silicate residue can be used for geopolymer production (Kaiser et al. 2021). The entire process is shown in *Figure 1*. Furthermore, the advantage of this process is that battery grade Li_2CO_3 can be obtained regardless of the feedstock used (primary or secondary - black mass). For instance, > 96 % of Li recovery was reached from black mass according to (Mende et al. 2023).

Figure 1. Process flow of the COOL+ process. (Mende et al. 2023; Kaiser et al. 2021; Martin et al. 2017; Pavón et al. 2021a)

METALLICO project aims to extract critical battery metals from primary and tailing materials through the development of cost-efficient processes. Hence, the COOL+ process provides a possible solution for the lithium production from local minerals and, considering the geographical boundaries contributes to securing the material base in Europe by reducing the import dependency.

In this work, spodumene was mixed with different concentrations of Na_2CO_3 to improve Li leaching. In the calcination process, Na_2CO_3 enhances lithium extraction by forming water-soluble compounds to improve the leaching of Li during the COOL+ process, enhancing Li_2CO_3 precipitation in the process. It also increases the kinetics of reaction leading to faster and more efficient extraction of Li. The homogeneous mixture with a particle size $\leq 250 \mu\text{m}$ was calcinated at 750 °C for 2 hours. The leaching using supercritical CO₂ was conducted in a high-pressure reactor for 3 hours at 100 bar and 230 °C. The solid residue was dried after the filtration step and used for geopolymer production. Further processing consists of concentrating the lithium species by electrodialysis and final precipitation

of Li_2CO_3 in battery grade. After the COOL+ Process, the calcinated solid mixture and solid residue were analyzed by XRD to investigate the phase transformation and quantitative analysis. To determine Li and other elements' recovery rates, the leaching solution was analyzed by ICP- OES and AAS.

During the calcination process, a new phase occurred, nepheline, whose concentration increases with the increase of Na_2CO_3 concentration in the mixture, making the silicate residue containing nepheline and albite a valid resource for geopolymer production. The use of geopolymers as construction materials, high-performance binders, waste stabilization and immobilization, 3D printing, insulating materials, and glass and ceramics production, makes them a very important product in the entire process cycle. The results show an increase in Li recovery proportionally to the amount of Na_2CO_3 with a maximum Li yield of 60 % using 30 wt.% of Na_2CO_3 . However, a further increase of Na_2CO_3 in the mixture leads to a decrease in Li recovery. With further optimization of the process (decreasing the particle size, l/s ratio, and reaction time), achieving more than 80 % of Li recovery is possible. Regarding the solid residue obtained after the CO_2 leaching, it can be confirmed that it is a valuable resource for geopolymer production since, during the calcination process, a new phase, nepheline, occurred whose concentration increases proportionally with the increase in Na_2CO_3 concentration of the mixture.

It is evident that the COOL+ process enables the Li extraction from spodumene and similar minerals, such as lepidolite, petalite, and zinnwaldite, and can be included in the circular economy due to the zero-waste principle (Bertau und Martin 2019). Solid residue as a generated waste, which is rich in aluminosilicates (albite and nepheline), can be used for geopolymer production.

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